

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Probability Distribution Fitting to Maternal Mortality Rates in Nigeria

I. A. Ogunsola¹, O. J. Akinpeloye², L. A. Dada³

¹Department of Statistics, Federal University of Agriculture, Abeokuta, Nigeria, ²Department of Epidemiology, University of Ibadan, Ibadan, Nigeria, ³Department of Statistics, University of Ibadan, Ibadan, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Maternal mortality causes loss of lives among others. In this work, we obtain the maternal mortality rates (MMR) in Nigeria, identify some fitted distributions to MMR, and determine which distribution best fits the data. The statistical methodology adopted in this research work is mainly probability distribution modeling approach. Method: A comprehensive exploratory data analysis was carried out on maternal mortality data collected and the MMR was obtained. The result shows that the rate was very high in 2012 and 2011 but a low rate was observed in 2014 indicating that some measures were put in place to control the situation and a sudden increase in 2015 and 2016 was also noticed suggesting a failure in some of the measures put in place in the previous years. Discussion: Two parameters gamma distribution, lognormal, Weibull, and exponential distributions were fitted for MMR. Both Bayesian information criterion (BIC) and Akaike information criterion (AIC) selection criteria were adopted in selecting the most fitted distribution. The AICs for gamma, lognormal, Weibull, and exponential distributions fitted for MMR were 1339.396, 1363.899, 1340.161, and 370.5244, respectively. Furthermore, the BICs for gamma, lognormal, Weibull and exponential distributions fitted for MMR were 1344.971, 1369.474, 1345.736, and 373.3119, respectively. Conclusion: It can be observed that exponential distribution has the least AIC (370.5244) and least BIC (373.3119); therefore, it is the most fitted distribution of all the distributions fitted for MMR. The estimate (standard error) of exponential distribution on MMR is 0.5853 indicating the fitness of the distribution being the one with the least standard error. In conclusion, the model obtained in this study can be used to study MMR in Nigeria to achieve a better economy and thus brings about local and national development. Future research can be extended to statistical analysis of the causes of maternal mortality.

Key words: Bayesian information criterion, Exploratory data analysis, Maternal mortality rates, Maternal mortality, Probability distribution

INTRODUCTION

The joy of every woman is to conceive and give birth to a bouncing baby bringing happiness to the family as a whole. This supposed to be a normal hitch-free physiological process from conception to birth in an ideal society. Most often, the converse is the case in some developing countries of the world like Nigeria. The situation has even worsen to cases where woman is often frightened and scared with conceiving and procreating due to the increase in maternal mortality rates (MMR)

in developing countries. In developing countries today, maternal mortality has been identified as one of the major causes of death among women of reproductive age and also remains one of the serious public health issues (WHO, 2007).

Maternal mortality is defined as the loss of life of a woman while pregnant or within 42 days of termination of pregnancy, irrespective of the site and duration of the pregnancy, from any cause traced or related to the pregnancy or its management but not from accidental or incidental causes. MMR is the number of maternal deaths per 100,000 live births. A lot of work has been done on maternal mortality in tertiary health institutions, which have a high selection of complicated cases. In Africa, 1 of 16 women stands the risk of dying

Address for correspondence:

O. J. Akinpeloye

E-mail: profisqeel@yahoo.com

through pregnancy and child birth. Questions as to what statistical model would be reliable for a comprehensive study of maternal mortality incidence in the facility need to be made evident. It is in light of developing a reliable statistical model to study maternal mortality makes this study germane. To obtain a true picture of the epidemiology of maternal mortality in Nigeria, this study was carried out in a tertiary health facility to which primary and secondary health-care facilities refer patients. The objectives of this work are to obtain the MMR in Nigeria, identify some fitted distributions to MMR, and determine which distribution best fits the data.^[1-5]

METHODOLOGY

The methodology adopted in this study is the probability distribution fitting approach [Figure 1]. Two parameters gamma distribution, lognormal, Weibull and exponential distributions were fitted for MMR. Both Bayesian information criterion (BIC) and AIC selection criteria were adopted in selecting the most fitted distribution.

MMR

MMR can be calculated using:

$$MMR = \frac{TMM}{TLB} \times 1000 \text{ Live births}$$

Where, MMR is MMR, TMM is total maternal mortality, and TLB is the total live births in a given period of time.

Exponential distribution

The exponential distribution is one of the widely used continuous distributions.^[6-9] It is often used to model the time elapsed between events. A continuous random variable X is said to have an exponential distribution with parameter $\lambda > 0$, shown as $x \sim \text{Exponential}(\lambda)$, if its PDF is given by:

$$f(x) = \begin{cases} \lambda e^{-\lambda x} & x > 0 \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

Where the variable x and the parameter λ are positive real quantities.

The mean and variance of exponential distributions is $\frac{1}{\lambda}$ and $\frac{1}{\lambda^2}$, respectively. Furthermore, using maximum likelihood, the estimator of the parameter λ is given as $\hat{\lambda} = \frac{n}{\sum_{i=1}^n x_i}$.

Weibull distribution

The Weibull distribution is named for Waloddi Weibull. Weibull was not the first person to use the distribution, but was the first to study it extensively and recognize its wide use in applications. The probability density function of a Weibull random variable is given as:

$$f_{\beta,\alpha}(x) = \begin{cases} \frac{\alpha}{\beta} \left(\frac{x}{\beta}\right)^{\alpha-1} e^{-\left(\frac{x}{\beta}\right)^\alpha}, & x \geq 0 \\ 0, & x < 0 \end{cases}$$

Using the method of moment or expectation method, the mean and variance of Weibull distribution is given as $\beta \left(1 + \frac{1}{\alpha}\right)$ and $\beta^2 \left(\Gamma\left(1 + \frac{2}{\alpha}\right) - \left[\Gamma\left(1 + \frac{1}{\alpha}\right) \right]^2 \right)$, respectively.

Using maximum likelihood, the estimator of the parameter α^* and β is given as:

$$\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^N x_i^\alpha = \beta^\alpha$$

and

$$\Rightarrow \alpha^* = \left[\frac{\sum_{i=1}^N x_i^{\alpha^*} \ln x_i}{\sum_{i=1}^N x_i^{\alpha^*}} - \ln x \right]^{-1}$$

This equation is only numerically solvable, for example, Newton-Raphson algorithm $\hat{\alpha}^*$ can be placed into $\hat{\beta}^*$ to complete the ML estimator for the Weibull distribution.

Gamma distribution

This is generally known as a distribution frequently used in waiting time modeling. Its Pdf is given as:

$$f_{\beta,\alpha}(x) = \begin{cases} x^{\alpha-1} e^{-\frac{x}{\beta}} & x > 0, \alpha > 0, \beta > 0 \\ \tilde{A}\alpha\beta^\alpha & \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

where the parameters α and β are positive real quantities as is the variable x . Note the parameter α is simply a scale factor. The mean and variance of gamma distribution is $\alpha\beta$ and $\alpha\beta^2$

Log-normal distribution

The lognormal distribution takes on both a two-parameter and three-parameter form. The density function for the two-parameter lognormal distribution is

$$f(X|\mu, \sigma^2) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{(2\pi\sigma^2)}X} \exp\left[-\frac{(\ln(X) - \mu)^2}{2\sigma^2}\right]$$

$$X > 0, \infty < \mu < \infty, \sigma > 0$$

The mean and variance of log normal distribution is $exp(2\mu+2\sigma^2)$ and

$$exp(2\mu + 2\sigma^2) - \left(exp\left(\mu + \frac{\sigma^2}{2}\right) \right)^2, \text{ respectively.}$$

The maximum likelihood estimators for μ and σ^2 are:

$$\hat{\mu} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \ln(X_i)$$

and

$$\hat{\sigma}^2 = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n \left(\ln(X_i) - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n \ln(X_i)}{n} \right)^2}{n}$$

MODEL SELECTION CRITERION

The selection criterion used in this research is Akaike information criterion (AIC) and BIC.

AIC and BIC are based on the maximum likelihood estimates of the model parameters

The correct formula for the AIC for a model with parameters $\beta_0, \beta_1, \dots, \beta_{p-1}$ and σ^2 is

$$AIC = -2 \log \text{likelihood} + 2p$$

and the correct formula for BIC is

$$BIC = n + n \log 2\pi + n \log(RSS/n) + (\log n)(p+1)$$

Where p is the number of parameters and RSS is the residual sum of squares.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Here, we discuss and present the analysis and results obtained. This is broadly divided into two sections, the descriptive section and the probability modeling section.

Descriptive statistics will summarize the data, histogram will help us know the pattern of the data and box plot to check whether there is outlier in the data or not and lastly exponential, gamma, lognormal, and Weibull distributions will also be fitted to mortality data to know the appropriate model with distribution that have minimum AIC and BIC.

Summary of maternal mortality data

MMR and all other subheadings is coming under Summary of maternal mortality data.

MMR

Table 1 shows the MMR in UCH between years under study. It can be deduced that high maternal mortality rate was recorded in the year 2012 with 8/1000 live birth.

Distribution for maternal mortality cases

A two parameters gamma, Weibull, exponential, and log-normal distribution is fitted into the total number of live birth cases and maternal mortality cases. The estimated parameters and their standard errors are obtained in preceding subsections.

Table 1: Maternal mortality rates

Year	Time(t)	TMM	TLB	MMR
2007	1	25	3389	7.3768=7
2008	2	16	3334	4.7990=5
2009	3	14	3071	4.5588=5
2010	4	18	2790	6.4516=7
2011	5	24	3005	7.9866=8
2012	6	27	3329	8.1105=8
2013	7	20	3339	5.9898=6
2014	8	14	3448	4.0603=4
2015	9	23	3387	6.7906=7
2016	10	24	3325	7.2180=7

Source: University College Hospital (UCH), Ibadan

Two parameters gamma distribution

Using maximum likelihood approach, the estimated parameters are derived from fitted distribution density.

$$f(x_t, \alpha, \beta) = \frac{x_t^{1.6538964-1} e^{-\frac{x_t}{0.01613350}}}{0.01613350^{1.6538964} \Gamma(1.6538964)} x_t > 0$$

The estimated for shape (α) is 1.6538964 with a standard error of 0.0161335 and the estimated value for rate (β) is 0.0161335 with a standard error of 0.194383987. The standard error of β is quite smaller than that of α .

Lognormal distribution

Adopting a log-normal distribution, the estimated mean log and log standard deviation with their standard error are given in Table 2.

The function for the studied time period is

$$f(x_t) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{0.00871010438646436A}} \exp \left[-\frac{1}{2} \frac{(\log x_t - 4.3163588)^2}{0.00871010438646436} \right]$$

The estimated for mean log (μ) is 4.3163588 with a standard error of 0.08519636 and the estimated value for log standard deviation (σ) is 0.09332794 with a standard error of 0.06024261. The standard error of these estimates is quite small which shows that the estimates are close to the parameter of interest [Tables 3 and 4].

Table 2: Estimated log normal parameter values with standard errors

Parameters & Errors	Mean log	Log standard deviation
Values	4.3163588	0.09332794
Standard error	0.08519636	0.06024261

Table 3: Summary of the data

Min.	1 st Qu.	Median	3 rd Qu	Max
0	0	1	3	7

Table 4: Estimated gamma parameter values with standard errors

Parameters & Errors	Shape	Rate
Values	1.6538964	0.01613350
Standard errors	0.9751826	0.03245623

Weibull distribution

Adopting a Weibull distribution, the estimated shape and scale standard deviation with their standard error are given in Table 5.

$$f(x_t, \alpha, \beta) = \frac{1.401204}{x_t} \left(\frac{x_t}{114.010785} \right)^{1.401204} e^{-\left(\frac{x_t}{114.010785} \right)} x_t > 0$$

The estimated for shape (α) is 1.401204 with a standard error of 0.1020607 and the estimated value for scale (β) is 114.010785 with a standard error of 7.8179819. The standard error of shape is smaller than that of scale parameter.

Exponential distribution

Fitting an exponential distribution into the data, the estimated rate parameter is given in Table 6.

The estimated rate (parameter) occurrences through maximum likelihood method are 0.5853659.

Thus, the distribution of the number of live birth recorded over the study is given below.

$$f(x_t, \lambda) = \frac{1}{0.5853659} e^{-\frac{x_t}{0.5853659}} x_t > 0$$

Where t is period between year understudy. The standard error of the parameter is 0.0008682863 which is quite small and it implies that the rate estimate is very close to the parameter.

Model Selection

In this section, we compute the AIC and the BIC to select the best model that fits the data. This will be done on the basis of the minimum AIC and BIC.

Table 5: Estimated Weibull parameter values with standard errors

Parameters & Errors	Shape	Scale
Values	1.401204	114.010785
Standard errors	0.1020607	7.8179819

Table 6: Estimated exponential parameter value with standard error

Parameters & Errors	Estimate	Standard error
Rate	0.5853659	0.05343619

Figure 1: Box plot and histogram of the live birth data

Table 7: AIC and BIC values of the distributions considered for MMR

Values	Gamma	Lognormal	Weibull	Exponential
AIC	1339.396	1363.899	1340.161	370.5244
BIC	1344.971	1369.474	1345.736	373.3119

Table 7 shows the computation of AIC and BIC of the four distributions used to fit the MMR. It reviewed that exponential distribution is the appropriate model for the data due to the smallest AIC and BIC when compared the AIC and BIC with one another, with the value of 370.5244 and 373.3119, respectively.

CONCLUSION

MMR is an important factor that affects the national economy, so its control must be put into consideration. Hence, the model obtained from this study can be used to monitor and study maternal mortality in Nigeria to achieve a better economy and thus brings about local and national development at large.

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